

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING BETWEEN

DataCite, Crossref, and the Africa PID Alliance

1. Introduction

Creating and supporting authoritative connections between researchers, their works, funding sources, and affiliations is crucial for facilitating public access to scholarly content. DataCite and Crossref, both non-profit organizations, are committed to supporting discoverability in scholarly communications. The Africa PID Alliance is dedicated to advancing persistent identifier (PID) usage across Africa, and shares the common goal of enhancing the accessibility of scholarly works. This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) outlines the collaborative efforts between DataCite, Crossref, and the Africa PID Alliance.

2. Background

DataCite (datacite.org) is an international not-for-profit membership organization and a global community that shares a common interest in ensuring that research outputs and resources are openly available and connected so that their reuse can advance knowledge across and between disciplines, now and in the future, and having its registered office in Germany which expression shall where the context so admits include its permitted representatives and assigns of the first part.

Crossref (crossref.org) is a not-for-profit membership association which provides a range of services to ensure that scholarly research metadata is registered, linked, and distributed, its registered office is 50 Salem Street, Lynnfield, MA, 10940 USA, which expression shall where the context so admits include its permitted representatives and assigns of the second part.

Africa PID Alliance (africapidalliance.org) serves as the primary initiative within the Open Infrastructure Program of the Training Centre in Communication, a research capacity Trust, based at the University of Nairobi, Kenya. The overarching goal of the

Africa PID Alliance is facilitating the provision of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Patent Data, Traditional Knowledge, and Cultural Heritage through its Digital Object Container Identifier (DOCiD™) (hereinafter referred to as "APA") which expression shall where the context so admits include its permitted representatives and assigns of the third part.

3. Purpose of the MOU

This MOU establishes a framework for collaboration between DataCite, Crossref, and the Africa PID Alliance to coordinate efforts in adopting identifiers and standards for managing access to and reporting of research outputs.

4. Areas of Collaboration

- Integration of Persistent Identifiers: Explore potential integration of services between DataCite, Crossref and the Africa PID Alliance.
- Awareness Building: Building awareness of respective services among researchers and administrators.
- Encouraging PID Open Infrastructure Usage: Encouraging the use of persistent identifier services for researchers and organizations to support public access to research outputs and resources.
- Linking Research Outputs, Researchers, Organisations and Funding: Supporting simple links between research outputs and resources, researchers, organisations and funding.
- Explore solutions to the inclusion of indigenous knowledge in the global scholarly record, including clear provenance for all works.

5. Operational Mechanisms

- Strategic Conversations: DataCite, Crossref and the Africa PID Alliance commit to regular strategic conversations at the leadership level to explore partnership possibilities.
- Engagement with Stakeholders: All parties will support specific engagement with relevant groups to further the goals outlined in this MOU.
- Coordinated Communications: Exploring options for coordinated communications regarding the intentions and outcomes of this MOU, including making this document publicly available.

- Financial Considerations: There will be no monetary exchange between DataCite, Crossref, and the Africa PID Alliance regarding this MOU or the activities described herein, for services or membership purposes.

6. Term and Termination

This MOU will be effective from the date of signature and remain in effect for two years, with the option to renew. Either party may decide to terminate the memorandum with a 30-day notice to the other party.

Signatories

Signed on behalf of **DataCite**:

Matthew Buys
Executive Director, DataCite
Date:

Signed on behalf of **Crossref**:

Ed Pentz
Executive Director, Crossref
Date:

Signed on behalf of the **Africa PID Alliance**:

Joy Owango,
Director, Africa PID Alliance
Date: